

An evaluation of climate adaptation policy in Britain and Ireland: what we can learn from our neighbours*

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Introduction

It has become apparent over the past decade that climate shocks and impacts cannot be halted by mitigation alone, and that planning for adaptation to climate change impacts must be a central focus of climate policies.¹ Adaptation policy is a broad concept and encompasses a number of aspects,² but overall the literature defines it as strategic, international to sub-national guidance and/or legislation pertaining to how sectors and geographies should adapt to current and future climate change. Divergences in policy development and implementation are indicative of differing political structures, socioeconomic conditions and values.³

Differing national governance structures also influence the role of sub-national governments, with some having

significant political and economic influence, whereas for other countries sub-national authorities have minimal ability to govern and make decisions.⁴ 'Policy coordination is a critical issue because climate change adaptation represents a complex, long-term, knowledge-intensive problem, which poses a significant cross-sectoral and multi-level decision-making challenge'.⁵

In terms of scale of adaptation policy, national governments are often highly influential in the policy agenda due to their coordination of budgets and financing of adaptation. National activity may relate to risk assessments, creating the evidence base to support action at lower levels, policy frameworks that influence decisions at subnational levels, coordination of the necessary legal frameworks, requesting specific sectoral action and providing resource to other levels of government to undertake these actions.⁶ Whilst national governments may set the policy agenda, at the subnational and local government scales there is often an expectation of coordination and implementation of actions.⁷ Where national governments do not provide a policy agenda (for example, the US and Australia), sub-national levels of government (in both these cases the states/territories) often set their own policy agendas.⁸ This adds to the complexity, especially when there is a lack of coordination across the different states/territories. As climate adaptation is often portrayed as an intrinsically local issue, local government and community action is often of particular importance, with municipalities playing a major role in adaptation implementation.⁹

In order to address the increasingly complex and numerous questions from across diverse policy sectors

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1 RH Moss *et al.* 'Climate change. Hell and high water: practice-relevant adaptation science' (2013) 8(342) *Science* 696; BL Preston, J Mustelin and MC Maloney 'Climate adaptation heuristics and the science/policy divide' (2015) 20(3) *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change* 467.

2 S Torjman *What is policy?* (Caledon Institute of Social Policy 2005). <<https://www.deslibris.ca/ID/202308>> (last accessed 2 March 2023).

3 TR Popp 'Explaining policy convergence and divergence through policy paradigm shifts: a comparative analysis of agricultural risk governance in OECD countries' (2021) 23(3) *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice* 310.

4 A. Connell, E St Denny and S Martin 'How can subnational governments develop and deliver distinctive policy agendas?' (2022) 88(4) *International Review of Administrative Sciences* 1159.

5 D Russel *et al.* 'Policy coordination for national climate change adaptation in Europe: all process, but little power' (2020) 12(13) *Sustainability* 5393.

6 L Berrang-Ford, JD Ford and J Paterson 'Are we adapting to climate change?' (2011) 21(1) *Global Environmental Change* 25; N Mimura *et al.* 'Adaptation planning and implementation' in *Climate Change 2014 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects*. Working Group II contribution to the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 2014).

7 Mimura *et al.* Note 6 above.

8 *ibid.*

9 J Corfee-Morlot *et al.* 'Cities, climate change and multilevel governance' OECD Environmental Working Papers No 14, 2009 (OECD Publishing 2009) © OECD <<https://www.oecd.org/env/cc/44242293.pdf>> (last accessed 10 October 2022); C Rosenzweig and W Solecki 'Introduction to climate change adaptation in New York City: building a risk management response: climate change adaptation in New York City' (2010) 1196(1) *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 13.

and scales ranging from local to global, a high level of co-ordination is necessary.¹⁰ The authors argue that it is effective climate adaptation policy that can enable this co-ordination among the various actors involved. Climate adaptation policy does not just set out guidelines and offer information on how society can adapt, it also provides the impetus for action towards climate adaptation. Reckien et al¹¹ found that cities with national mandates to develop plans are 1.8 times more likely to have a mitigation plan and five times more likely to have an adaptation plan (although this was dependent on the length of time the national policy was in place). Dilling et al¹² found that the most effective motivator of climate adaptation in municipal areas in several US States was external incentives, either pressure or funding from a higher government level, which is supported by studies across different municipal areas in Europe¹³ and Latin America.¹⁴ On a national scale the idea of a higher-level mandate is also evident; with many countries accepting obligations to put in place national climate adaptation measures only after international drivers such as the European Union (EU) adaptation strategy¹⁵ or the Paris Agreement¹⁶ were implemented. This shows how a ‘top-down’ approach can be beneficial in adaptation policy development, although it is essential that it is used alongside a ‘bottom-up’ approach in order to include diverse stakeholder participation, fair representation at every level and overall increased capacity for climate action.¹⁷

10 R Klein et al. ‘Advancing climate adaptation practices and solutions: emerging research priorities’ SEI Working Paper 2017-07 (Stockholm, Sweden 2017).

11 D Reckien et al. ‘How are cities planning to respond to climate change? Assessment of local climate plans from 885 cities in the EU-28’ (2018) 191 *Journal of Cleaner Production* 207.

12 L Dilling et al. ‘Drivers of adaptation: responses to weather- and climate-related hazards in 60 local governments in the Intermountain Western U.S.’ (2017) 49(11) *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space* 2628.

13 H Amundsen, F Berglund and H Westskog ‘Overcoming barriers to climate change adaptation – a question of multilevel governance?’ (2010) 28(2) *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy* 276; JJ Porter, D Demeritt and S Dessai ‘The right stuff? Informing adaptation to climate change in British local government’ (2015) 35 *Global Environmental Change* 411.

14 J Hardoy and PR Lankao ‘Latin American cities and climate change: challenges and options to mitigation and adaptation responses’ (2011) 3(3) *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 158; H Kim and S Grafakos ‘Which are the factors influencing the integration of mitigation and adaptation in climate change plans in Latin American cities?’ (2019) 14(10) *Environmental Research Letters* 105008 <<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab2f4c>> (last accessed 27 January 2023).

15 European Commission, Communication on forging a climate-resilient Europe – the new EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change, COM(2021) 82, 24 February, 2021.

16 Paris Agreement to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 12 December 2015, T.I.A.S. No 16-1104.

17 D Conway et al. ‘The need for bottom-up assessments of climate risks and adaptation in climate-sensitive regions’ (2019) 9(7) *Nature Climate Change* 503; J Sweeney ‘Climate change in Ireland: science, impacts and adaptation’ in D Robbins, D Torney and P Brereton (eds) *Ireland and the Climate Crisis* (Palgrave Macmillan 2020).

Implementation research has made clear that goals and objectives contained in law and policy documents often stay on paper because of the numerous obstacles that plague implementation processes.¹⁸ While there are numerous factors that can impact effective adaptation, it is important to realise that many of these factors are often place-based and context-specific. In this article we seek to interrogate the national climate adaptation policies of Ireland and the UK (England, Northern Ireland, Wales, Scotland), each of which is facing similar climate impacts and has similar governance structures, to see to what extent national policies can address, and have addressed, these different factors in order to enable adaptation action in practice.

National bodies containing climate experts are commonly used by governments to design and deliver climate objectives.¹⁹ In Ireland and the UK bodies such as the Climate Change Advisory Council (CCAC) and the Climate Change Committee (CCC) carry out annual progress reviews and reports based on the goals set by the respective government authorities. However, these reports are often focused on the views of academics and government officials and do not generally represent the views of adaptation practitioners and third sector actors. As highlighted through the work of Walker et al²⁰ there tends to be among experts a shared imagination of ‘the public’, one that is influenced by secondhand narratives as well as real world interactions. It is this view of ‘the public’ which policymakers are using to create plans and strategies that will determine the direction of our climate adaptation priorities and ambition. To ensure that this shared concept is as representative as possible, the approach we have taken brings together a range of different stakeholders from the field of climate adaptation and climate action and allows for a comprehensive dialogue on the shortcomings and benefits of policies in each jurisdiction, building a bridge between different knowledge actors.

To see how each jurisdiction (Ireland, England, Northern Ireland, Wales, Scotland) is preparing for the current and future impacts of climate change and how, or if, high-level governance is driving this, we created an assessment framework to evaluate the national adaptation strategies of each country. This framework was created following a review of existing adaptation literature, with recurring themes and key concepts on what defines and is

18 PL Hupe ‘The thesis of incongruent implementation: revisiting Pressman and Wildavsky’ (2011) 26(1) *Public Policy and Administration* 63.

19 J Christensen and K Serrano Velarde ‘The role of advisory bodies in the emergence of cross-cutting policy issues: comparing innovation policy in Norway and Germany’ (2019) 20(1) *European Politics and Society* 49.

20 G Walker et al. ‘Renewable energy and sociotechnical change: imagined subjectivities of “the public” and their implications’ (2010) 42(4) *Environment and Planning A* 931.

necessary for best practice adaptation policy included as central dimensions of the framework.

To validate these findings and address the gap that exists between academic and ‘on the ground’ practitioner knowledge and the perspectives different stakeholders have of adaptation measures,²¹ this research used a modified Delphi method approach. The iterative nature of the Delphi approach allows participants to reconsider their original responses in light of the knowledge and opinions expressed by other Delphi panel participants. Our modified Delphi approach further differs from traditional surveys by allowing for the facilitation of social learning, following the generation of a much more robust information base provided in the initial interaction, and the interactions in each round following this.²²

The evolution of climate adaptation policy in each of the five jurisdictions, outlined in McCullagh et al,²³ plays an important role in understanding how various institutional barriers or enablers are hindering or supporting the operationalisation of climate adaptation, and these factors are further considered in the discussion section. This research seeks to provide a current baseline, generated by a broad range of representative stakeholder insights, for decision-makers in the respective governments to begin addressing areas where essential criteria for adaptation are not recognised in policy. However, it will also highlight areas where national adaptation policies are meeting and exceeding ambitions and where these successes can be implemented elsewhere.

Methodology

Framework design

Successful climate adaptation policy is defined by the present authors as ‘the creation and implementation of flexible and dynamic policies that are set within the broader social, economic and cultural environment and allow for sustainable development in a way that does not cause further inequality’.²⁴ Moreover, ‘effective’ climate adaptation policy is considered as policy that should help to overcome factors that could provide barriers to adaptation. While drivers and barriers can be context-

specific or on a continuum,²⁵ social conditions, cultural influences, natural processes and physical patterns all have an impact on adaptation efforts. Based on this information, the framework developed had 33 criteria under five key themes, encompassing a range of dimensions (Table 1). Throughout the literature these themes and their subsequent dimensions, outlined below, while by no means exhaustive, have been found time and time again to be important for effective and just adaptation policies.

Stakeholder engagement

In order to ensure that maladaptation does not exacerbate existing inequalities within society, it is essential that climate adaptation is done with and not to people. Social inclusion and stakeholder engagement is, therefore, crucial in any adaptation policy development and multi-disciplinary methods of engaging with different groups have been developed over the past decades.²⁶

Policy and governance

National policy. Provides a clear agenda, structure and guidance to enable climate action at all levels (national to local) and across all sectors. High-level policy and guidance, in particular, provides a starting point, allowing for more outcome and action orientated ambition over time, while also providing an obligation on a range of sectors and organisations to consider climate adaptation in their operating procedures.

Leadership and co-ordination of roles and responsibilities. When institutional governance and decision-making structures are inappropriate or ineffective, this can restrict adaptation policy development and implementation.²⁷ A multi-level governance approach that provides the potential for adaptation champions, within any sphere of influence, and the impetus to commence and sustain

21 A Revez, JA Cortes-Vazquez and S Flood ‘Risky policies: local contestation of mainstream flood risk management approaches in Ireland’ (2017) 49(11) *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space* 2497.

22 S Flood et al. ‘Adaptive and interactive climate futures: systematic review of “serious games” for engagement and decision-making’ (2018) 13(6) *Environmental Research Letters* < <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/aac1c6> > (last accessed 10 March 2023).

23 D McCullagh et al. ‘Transboundary adaptation learning exchange’ (2023) Report. (in the press) Environmental Protection Agency, Ireland.

24 ibid.

25 S Moser and JA Ekstrom ‘A framework to diagnose barriers to climate change adaptation’ (2010) 107 (51) *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 22026; D Reckien et al. ‘The influence of drivers and barriers on urban adaptation and mitigation plans – an empirical analysis of European cities’ (2015) *PLoS ONE* 10 <<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0135597>> (last accessed 16 February 2023).

26 MB Abbott and A Jonski ‘The democratisation of decision-making processes in the water sector II’ (2001) 3(1) *Journal of Hydroinformatics* 35; K Brown ‘Innovation for conservation and development’ (2002) 168 *The Geographical Journal* 6; JP Bousset, C Macombe and M Taverne ‘Participatory methods, guidelines and good practice guidance to be applied throughout the project to enhance problem definition, co-learning, synthesis and dissemination’ (2005) SEAMLESS Report No 10, SEAMLESS integrated project, EU 6th Framework Programme, contract no 010036-2, 248 pp, ISBN no. 90-8585-038-X <www.SEAMLESS-IP.org> (last accessed 4 April 2023); L Basco Carrera and A Giardino ‘Collaborative modelling or participatory modelling? A framework for water resources management’ (2017) 91 *Environmental Modelling and Software* 95.

27 L Berrang-Ford and SJ Heymann ‘What drives national adaptation? A global assessment’ (2014) 124(1–2) *Climatic Change* 441; M Araos et al. ‘Climate change adaptation planning in large cities: a systematic global assessment’ (2016) 66 *Environmental Science & Policy* 375.

climate action, enables adaptation solutions that are fair and balanced.²⁸

Climate justice and equity. This is one of the most crucial challenges facing adaptation policies. However, it also presents an opportunity to investigate inequalities in society and to ensure that all climate adaptation actions are fair and that further inequality is not exacerbated through the process of climate adaptation. By adopting measures which reduce the impacts of climate change to those who are most at risk, policies can prevent the most vulnerable in society from being further disadvantaged.

Resources

Staff and financing. Adaptation is a long-term process that will require appropriate support in the form of sustained funding and knowledgeable staff. Economic and human resource restrictions can limit adaptation progress by restricting the means for adaptation, influencing the use of finances or limiting the means to make the financial case for adaptation.²⁹ However, financing is not infinite and it is important that staff prioritise action where it will have the greatest impact. Adaptation policies can support access to appropriate resourcing in terms of finance and trained staff at a number of levels, as well as driving adaptation priorities, to ensure adaptation is successful.

Capacity-building and understanding the capability of decision-makers and action-takers. Climate adaptation is not always the main skillset of people managing the work, and acts as a barrier to the effective recording of outputs and outcomes.³⁰ This can lead to an 'adaptive capacity' gap between the perception that people are able and need to adapt and actually taking adaptive action to the level needed, leading to an 'adaptation deficit'.³¹ Adaptation policy can encourage the necessary characteristics that actors need to plan and deliver current and future work, by promoting the education, empowerment and engagement of all stakeholders across every level.

Information and data. A thorough scientific evidence base is a prerequisite for designing and implementing effective adaptation measures; however, access and availability to well-supported and informed adaptation data and policies can often be variable. By identifying where there is a lack

of knowledge, adaptation policy can drive clear research priorities setting out and promoting ambitious goals in order to close these gaps and inform decision-making.

Communication and guidance. The way climate change data are presented to decision-makers and policymakers can influence judgments about future climate scenarios and therefore adaptation decision-making.³² It is vital that presentation of data is tailored to the audience, ensuring that learning from cognitive and psychological sciences is used to improve accessibility.³³ To enable this, adaptation policy can promote the use of platforms that make information available to a wide and diverse audience, through open databases, knowledge brokers, policy entrepreneurs, bridging organisations, actions to support the coproduction of knowledge between science and practice and actions that build trust and social cohesion in communities.³⁴

Decision-making processes and uncertainty

Uncertainty in the adaptation decision-making context can be due to human decisions that affect climate change, the variability of the climate system and an incomplete understanding of climate projections and impacts and uncertainty regarding consequences of policies and interventions.³⁵ Adaptation policy provides for the ability to act now on the information available, regardless of decision uncertainty.

Mainstreaming and competing priorities

Climate impacts will exacerbate pre-existing stresses and there is a need to consider these linkages within strategies. It is important to consider how adaptation fits into development, considering both short- and long-term benefits and this may be explored through understanding linkages between adaptation, development and disaster risk management and identifying co-benefits amongst

28 A Jordan *et al.* 'Emergence of polycentric climate governance and its future prospects' (2015) 5 *Nature Climate Change* <10.1038/nclimate2725> (last accessed 26 March 2023).

29 C Oberlack and K Eisenack 'Alleviating barriers to urban climate change adaptation through international cooperation' (2014) 24 *Environmental Change* 349.

30 K Power *et al.* 'Adaptation actions in cities: what works?' Report of research findings (2018) AECOM and Sniffer <<https://www.theccc.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Adaptation-actions-in-cities-what-works-final.pdf>> (last accessed 4 April 2023).

31 Berang-Ford and Heymann (Note 27 above); A Lesnikowski *et al.* 'How are we adapting to climate change? A global assessment' (2015) 20(2) *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*

277; D Gawith and A Daigneault 'Climate change costs more than we think because people adapt less than we assume' (2020) 173 *Ecological Economics* 106636 <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106636>> (last accessed 4 April 2023).

32 JD Daron *et al.* 'Interpreting climate data visualisations to inform adaptation decisions' (2015) 10 *Climate Risk Management* 17.

33 J Harold *et al.* 'Cognitive and psychological science insights to improve climate change data visualization' (2016) 6(12) *Nature Climate Change* 1080.

34 J Cinner *et al.* 'Building adaptive capacity to climate change in tropical coastal communities' (2018) 8(2) *Nature Climate Change* 117; J Tribbia and SC Moser 'More than information: what coastal managers need to plan for climate change' (2008) 11(4) *Environmental Science & Policy* 315.

35 BL Van and JP Van der Sluijs 'Dealing with uncertainty in climate adaptation decision-making' in TC Lourenço *et al.* (eds) *Adapting to an uncertain climate: lessons from practice* (Springer, Berlin 2014) pp 17–40; M Catenacci and C Giupponi 'Potentials of Bayesian networks to deal with uncertainty in climate change adaptation policies' CMCC Research Paper No 70 (2009). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1526605> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1526605> (last accessed 27 March 2023).

societal goals.³⁶ For adaptation to become routine, it needs to be mainstreamed into the business-as-usual activities within organisations when delivering its functions. However, competing priorities and misalignment between various sectors must be recognised and managed to avoid maladaptation. Policy can support the mainstreaming of adaptation by decision-makers.

Delphi survey design

The Delphi method is a commonly used technique to structure group discussions in order to represent the genuine beliefs of a panel and is particularly useful on the subject of complex problems.³⁷ A panel of experts engages in multiple rounds of iterative anonymous discussion, in order to reach consensus and present a unified position on

a specific topic.³⁸ The dialogue and feedback process used in the Delphi technique allows respondents to reflect on their initial opinions, learn from the reasoning of others, and reconsider their own stance.³⁹

The Delphi survey used in this research was modified in a number of ways. It included a hybrid application of quantitative and qualitative methods⁴⁰ allowing for a more rounded view of real-world climate adaptation challenges. As well as this, the first round of the survey did not begin with the typical ‘open’ questions. Instead the authors used international best practice to provide initial assessments in a comprehensive framework, discussed in detail in the results section below. Subsequent rounds then allowed for expert panelists to adjust these assessments and to create or revise justifications. This allowed for a two-way learning exchange

Table 1. Framework used to assess the national climate adaption policies of all five

Theme	Sub-theme	Code	Criteria
Stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder engagement	S1	Representative stakeholder involvement throughout the entire climate adaptation process, from the creation of adaptation policy to the implementation and evaluation of adaptation plans
		S2	A dedicated process in place to facilitate inclusive stakeholder involvement in the preparation of adaptation policies
Policy and governance	National policy	P1	A central administration body officially in charge of adaptation policy-making
		P2	A national climate adaptation policy
		P3	Country level legislation in place to underpin adaptation policy (including frameworks and strategies)
		P4	Independent monitoring and evaluation of national policy
	Leadership and co-ordination of roles and responsibilities	P5	Horizontal (cross-sectoral) coordination mechanisms exist within the governance system, with division of responsibilities and SMART objectives and the alignment of policies
		P6	Vertical (multi-level) coordination mechanisms exist within the governance system, enabling all levels of administration from local to national to influence policy-making
		P7	Creation of spaces for leaders of climate adaptation to emerge across scales
		P8	Climate adaptation is scalable, able to be tailored to different levels
		P9	Transparent climate finance with regards to adaptation initiatives
		P10	Transboundary cooperation (either existing or planned) to work together to address common challenges with other countries
	Climate justice and equity	P11	Domestic justice and equity issues (economic, social, environmental and cultural), relevant to each country, are recognised in national-level climate change policy and implementation (for example through decision-making)
		P12	Processes are in place to allow actions to reduce any identified differences and/or ensure that the benefits of interventions accrue to the most vulnerable
		P13	Climate adaptation policy development, implementation and review is fully transparent

36 Mimura *et al.* (Note 6 above).

37 HA Linstone and M Turoff *The Delphi Method*. (Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley 1975); S Masse, PP Marchand and M Bernier-Cardou ‘Forecasting the deployment of short-rotation intensive culture of willow or hybrid poplar: insights from a Delphi study’ (2014) 44(5) *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* <<https://doi.org/10.1139/cjfr-2013-0364>> (last accessed 27 March 2023).

38 JS Richey, BW Mar and RR Horner ‘Delphi technique in environmental assessment. I. Implementation and effectiveness’ (1985) 21(2) *Journal of Environmental Management* 105; I Oliver ‘An expert panel-based approach to the assessment of vegetation condition within the

context of biodiversity conservation: stage 1: the identification of condition indicators’ (2002) 2(3) *Ecological Indicators* 223; M Makkonen, T Hujala and J Uusivuori ‘Policy experts’ propensity to change their opinion along Delphi rounds’ (2016) 109 *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 61.

39 C Hsu and BA Sandford ‘The Delphi technique: making sense of consensus’ (2007) 12(10) *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation* <<https://scholarworks.umass.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1177&context=pars>> accessed 2 October 2022.

40 G Rowe and G Wright ‘The Delphi technique: past, present, and future prospects. Introduction to the special issue’ (2011) 78 *Technical Forecasting and Social Change* 1487.

Resources	Staff and financing	R1	Appropriate financing (enough to cover the cost of policy actions) is being applied to climate adaptation to achieve policy goals at all levels of governance
		R2	Accessible long-term and self-sustaining resources are available to support policy goals at increasing climate resilience (that is, funding, infrastructure, human resources)
	Capacity building and understanding the capability of decision-makers and action takers	R3	Policy supports education, empowerment and engagement of stakeholders at all levels of decision-making and action-taking in relation to adaptation
		R4	Mechanisms exist to recruit and train practitioners with the specific skills required to undertake complex climate adaptation
	Information and data	R5	The policy supports advances in scientific research to improve understanding and inform decision-making
		R6	Guidance on how to employ climate adaptation information is provided at sub-national levels
	Communication and guidance	R7	Communication and engagement strategies included in the policy that utilise multiple platforms in order to reach diverse stakeholders
		R8	Recognition in the policy that climate change is an international issue and that adaptation strategies must look beyond national boundaries (that is, the policy ensures that the international aspect of adaptation is considered at decision-making levels)
		R9	Learning and support networks are available to enable all decision-makers in producing and implementing appropriate climate adaptation policies
Decision-making	Decision-making process and uncertainty	D1	Priority adaptation options are identified, prioritised and selected based on robust, equitable and transparent methods (for example, using decision support tools)
		D2	An evaluation process is in place to assess the effectiveness of actions taken across all aspects of climate adaptation (that is, from stakeholder engagement to mainstreaming)
		D3	The policy recognises that adaptation is an iterative and flexible process that accounts for new information and experience
Mainstreaming	Mainstreaming and competing priorities	M1	Consideration of climate change adaptation been included in the national frameworks for environmental impact assessments and DRRs (Disaster Risk Reduction)
		M2	Key policies recognise the need for adaptation action in future growth and development as a result of the impacts of climate change
		M3	National policy instruments promote adaptation at sectoral level, in line with national priorities
		M4	Adaptation is mainstreamed in insurance or alternative policy instruments to provide incentives for investment in risk prevention
		M5	Climate mitigation and adaptation are being investigated in tandem
		M6	Adaptation actions are sustainable (that is, they meet environmental, societal and cultural needs) for their intended lifetime

between the authors and the Delphi participants and a more robust discussion around the adaptation policy assessments.

Ethical approval was sought from the Social and Ethics Committee at University College Cork as part of this survey, in order to reassure participants that the survey would be carried out to the highest standards, promoting honest, rigorous and transparent research.

Figure 1 outlines the steps taken to complete the Delphi survey. Strong agreement among the panel members, across a majority of the criteria, meant that the Delphi process was concluded after round 2, as it was determined that further rounds would not achieve consensus on criteria that were particularly contentious, where panelists held strong opinions that were unlikely to be swayed.

The number of participants in each panel varied between jurisdiction areas; however, a total of 47 participants agreed to participate in the Delphi survey across all jurisdictions. These participants were working across a range of sectors, but were all

actively involved in the field of climate adaptation in the UK or Ireland. Participants were involved in the Delphi panel process from October 2021 until May 2022.

Table 2 outlines the number of panelists by jurisdiction, and the drop-off rate in participation between rounds, while

Table 3 outlines the range of participants who took part in the survey, all of whom were selected through the method of snowball sampling in order to increase access to those with high levels of climate adaptation knowledge in the various jurisdictions.

Table 4 outlines the experience level of the Delphi panel participants in the field of climate adaptation for each jurisdiction.

To capture and synthesise the wide range of responses discussed by the Delphi panel respondents over the rounds and to help frame the amended ratings and justifications, the authors focused on the assessment (colour) rating provided by the participants, as well as the content and

Figure 1. Policy assessment and Delphi survey methodology steps.

context of the justification. Three separate colour ratings were employed by the project team: red when the criterion is not acknowledged in policy, amber when the criterion is acknowledged in policy but not provided for in practice, and blue when the criterion is acknowledged in policy and is provided for in practice. To gain understanding and insight into the extent to which statements were changed between the rounds of the Delphi panel, a simple scoring metric was applied. Using a method based on that employed by McGookin et al,⁴¹ it assigned a representative weighting to the different types of restructuring or editing undertaken, to give an indicative gauge of the justifications that underwent the most significant changes. The higher the score the more profound the change in the justification. The scoring system is outlined in Table 5.

Results

The climate adaptation policy assessments highlighted key areas that were similar across the five jurisdictions, with all themes showing at least some level of agreement between jurisdictions. However, there are also stark differences in the assessments of some criteria, depending on the jurisdiction. The key findings, similarities and differences under each of the themes are presented in the following sub-sections, with the final assessment results presented in Table 6.

It is important to note that, following the completion of the Delphi survey, climate legislation came into effect in Northern Ireland that has impacted directly on three of the criteria (P3, P4 and P11) in the findings of the Delphi

Table 2. Number of responses and the associated response rate for two rounds of consultation within each jurisdiction.

Ireland		England		Northern Ireland		Wales		Scotland	
Round 1	Round 2	Round 1	Round 2	Round 1	Round 2	Round 1	Round 2	Round 1	Round 2
12 (100%)	12 (100%)	8 (100%)	6 (75%)	9 (100%)	5 (56%)	6 (100%)	6 (100%)	12 (100%)	9 (75%)

41 C McGookin, BÓ Gallachóir and E Byrne 'An innovative approach for estimating energy demand and supply to inform local energy transitions'

(2021) 229 *Energy* 120731 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544221009798> (last accessed 3 February 2023).

Table 3. Range of Delphi panel participant from each jurisdiction.

Country	Delphi panel participants' expertise by role (%)			
	<i>Policymaker</i>	<i>Practitioner</i>	<i>Academic/researcher</i>	<i>Other</i>
<i>Ireland</i>	12.5	12.5	66.7	8.3
<i>Scotland</i>	50	16.7	16.7	16.7
<i>Northern Ireland</i>	33.3	16.7	5.6	44.4
<i>Wales</i>	8.3	16.7	33.3	41.7
<i>England</i>	25	37.5	31.2	6.3
Total	27.7	19.1	31.9	21.3

Table 4. Level of experience of Delphi panel participants.

Country	Years of experience (% of participants in each range)			
	<i>1–3 years</i>	<i>4–10 years</i>	<i>11–15 years</i>	<i>16+ years</i>
<i>Ireland</i>	8.3	25	25	41.7
<i>Scotland</i>	25	41.6	16.7	16.7
<i>Northern Ireland</i>	11.1	33.3	33.3	22.3
<i>Wales</i>	33.3	16.7	16.7	33.3
<i>England</i>	12.5	12.5	25	50

Table 5. Scoring system used for analysis of Delphi participant responses.

Qualitative analysis	Score	Definition
Agreement without justification	0	where panelists did not provide a justification, suggesting they agreed with the assessment rating based upon the same points provided by the authors
Clarity of justification	1	minor points that were changed in the revision to better frame the justification, while still in agreement with the rating
Adding more context	3	changes/additions framing the justification and providing more context while in agreement with the rating
Complete change	5	entirely new rating and justification created after total disagreement

survey. These changes, and what they mean for Northern Ireland, will be discussed in greater detail in the next part of the article.

Stakeholder engagement

In all countries stakeholder engagement was felt to be either acknowledged in policy and not provided for in practice or acknowledged in policy and provided for in practice, although in Northern Ireland participants felt stakeholder engagement was not provided for in practice, with participant 4 noting 'Stakeholder engagement and scrutiny by non-departmental or independent stakeholders is not in place'. England and Scotland each had a criterion downgraded following the Delphi survey; however, criteria ratings remained broadly similar overall.

Policy and governance

Under national policy, all countries except Northern Ireland were rated as blue, suggesting that climate adaptation policy not only acknowledges but provides for aspects of national policy. Northern Ireland was assessed as having no climate legislation or independent monitoring in place, with policy failing to acknowledge the need for this. The only rating changes after the Delphi panel were in Scotland, where independent monitoring and evaluation was downgraded to amber, and England, where it was felt that although policy acknowledged the need for a central administration body, in reality this was not provided for, with the duties being split between a number of agencies. Participant 12 noted that,

Whilst the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) is officially the central coordinating point for adaptation policy across government, it lacks the levers needed to influence adaptation policymaking in many sector areas, so is in charge in name only.

Under 'leadership and the co-ordination of roles and responsibilities' there was a range of ratings from across different countries. All countries felt that transboundary cooperation was both acknowledged and provided for, and that vertical coordination and the creation of spaces for leaders were acknowledged in policy but not provided for, something which remained the same following the Delphi survey. Horizontal coordination was acknowledged in policy by all countries, but, following the Delphi survey, only in Wales was it provided for in practice. Initially the scalability of climate adaptation was rated as amber by all countries except England and Wales; however, following the Delphi survey, these criteria were downgraded to amber in England and Wales and downgraded to red in Northern Ireland. The transparency of climate finance was an area where jurisdictions differed a lot. In Scotland this was assessed as not being acknowledged in policy, in Ireland it was assessed as being acknowledged in policy and provided for in practice, while in the other jurisdictions it was assessed as being acknowledged in policy but not provided for in practice. This was further downgraded in Northern Ireland following the Delphi survey.

'Climate justice and equity' was assessed as either acknowledged in policy and not provided for, or acknowledged in policy and provided for in practice by all countries except Northern Ireland, who assessed this theme as unacknowledged in policy under all criteria, with participant 16 stating that 'climate equity and justice are missing from National Policies'. Following suggestions from the Delphi panel there was a change in one criterion rating in Wales from blue to amber.

Resources

'Staff and financing' was assessed the same by all countries with criteria either not acknowledged in policy or acknowledged in policy but not provided for in practice and did not experience any changes following the Delphi survey.

'Capacity building' was broadly felt to be either acknowledged in policy and not provided for or acknowledged in policy with provided for in practice, by all countries.

'Information and data' was felt to be acknowledged in policy and provided for in practice by Ireland, England and Wales, whereas the other jurisdictions' assessments outlined that while acknowledged in policy it was not always provided for in practice. This was downgraded to amber in both England and Wales following the Delphi panelists' recommendations. As outlined by participant 3 in Wales,

there is a risk in terms of where the funding to support the research is going to come from, especially with the removal of the EU funding structures. There is a need to ensure that there is funding to support advances in scientific knowledge and climate adaptation research.

'Communication and guidance' was generally assessed as being acknowledged in policy but not provided for. Although some criteria were assessed as being both acknowledged and provided for in Ireland, this was only supported by 50 per cent of participants, with participant 10 noting that 'While Climate Ireland provides an excellent service it is underfunded and not fit for purpose in its ability to provide the level and details of support needed'. However, there were three ratings changes following the Delphi panel, with Ireland, England and Wales each downgrading a criterion to amber.

Decision-making

There was complete agreement by all countries under decision-making in the initial assessment, with all countries stating that while the importance of decision-making is recognised in policy it is not provided for in reality. This is due to a number of factors including, competing priorities, limited budget, a lack of expertise and underutilised decision support tools. Following the recommendations of the Delphi panelists one criterion was downgraded to red in both Northern Ireland and Scotland during the second Delphi round, with participant 7 in Scotland noting the need for this, as 'options appear to be merely self-identified by the relevant lead organisation. Little evidence of appraisal undertaken, or of any resulting prioritisation'.

Mainstreaming

Mainstreaming was generally assessed as being acknowledged in policy but not provided for by all countries in the initial assessment, with some criteria, such as the recognition and promotion of adaptation by key policy and policy instruments, not only acknowledged but provided for in a number of jurisdictions. However, in Northern Ireland, the assessment indicated that there are criteria that are still not acknowledged in policy as necessary, including the investigation of mitigation and adaptation in tandem, with participant 5 noting that 'at a national level there is a lack of clarity regarding these being investigated in tandem', and the consideration of adaptation in key frameworks for EIAs and DRRs. Following the Delphi survey, the criterion 'key policies acknowledging the need for adaptation action' was downgraded from amber to red in England. The criterion 'there is consideration of adaptation in key frameworks for EIAs and DRRs' was upgraded from red to amber in Northern Ireland, the only criterion to be upgraded during the Delphi survey.

Table 6. Final assessment results after Delphi survey.

Theme	Sub-theme	Code	Criteria	I	E	N	W	S
Stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder engagement	S1	Representative stakeholder involvement throughout the entire climate adaptation process, from the creation of adaptation policy to the implementation and evaluation of adaptation plans					
		S2	A dedicated process in place to facilitate inclusive stakeholder involvement in the preparation of adaptation policies					
Policy and governance	National policy	P1	A central administration body officially in charge of adaptation policy making					
		P2	A national climate adaptation policy					
		P3	Country level legislation in place to underpin adaptation policy (including frameworks and strategies)					
		P4	Independent monitoring and evaluation of national policy					
	Leadership and co-ordination of roles and responsibilities	P5	Horizontal (cross-sectoral) coordination mechanisms exist within the governance system, with division of responsibilities and SMART objectives and the alignment of policies					
		P6	Vertical (multi-level) coordination mechanisms exist within the governance system, enabling all levels of administration from local to national to influence policy-making					
		P7	Creation of spaces for leaders of climate adaptation to emerge across scales					
		P8	Climate adaptation is scalable, able to be tailored to different levels					
		P9	Transparent climate finance with regards to adaptation initiatives					
		P10	Transboundary cooperation (either existing or planned) to work together to address common challenges with other countries					
	Climate justice and equity	P11	Domestic justice and equity issues (economic, social, environmental and cultural), relevant to each country, are recognised in national-level climate change policy and implementation (for example through decision-making)					
		P12	Processes are in place to allow actions to reduce any identified differences and/or ensure the benefits of interventions accrue to the most vulnerable					
		P13	Climate adaptation policy development, implementation and review is fully transparent					
Resources	Staff and financing	R1	Appropriate financing (enough to cover the cost of policy actions) is being applied to climate adaptation to achieve policy goals at all levels of governance					
		R2	Accessible long-term and self-sustaining resources are available to support policy goals at increasing climate resilience (that is, funding, infrastructure, human resources)					
	Capacity-building and understanding the capability of decision-makers and action-takers	R3	Policy supports education, empowerment and engagement of stakeholders at all levels of decision-making and action-taking in relation to adaptation					
		R4	Mechanisms exist to recruit and train practitioners with the specific skills required to undertake complex climate adaptation					
	Information and data	R5	The policy supports advances in scientific research to improve understanding and inform decision-making					
		R6	Guidance for how to employ climate adaptation information is provided at sub-national levels					
	Communication and guidance	R7	Communication and engagement strategies included within the policy that utilise multiple platforms in order to reach diverse stakeholders					
		R8	Recognition in the policy that climate change is an international issue and that adaptation strategies must look beyond national boundaries (that is, the policy ensures the international aspect of adaptation is considered at decision-making levels)					
		R9	Learning and support networks are available to enable all decision-makers in producing and implementing appropriate climate adaptation policies					

Decision-making	Decision-making process and uncertainty	D1	Priority adaptation options are identified, prioritised and selected based on robust, equitable and transparent methods (for example, using decision support tools)	Amber	Amber	Red	Amber	Red
		D2	An evaluation process is in place to assess the effectiveness of actions taken across all aspects of climate adaptation (that is, from stakeholder engagement to mainstreaming)	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber
		D3	The policy recognises that adaptation is an iterative and flexible process that accounts for new information and experience	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber
Mainstreaming	Mainstreaming and competing priorities	M1	Consideration of climate change adaptation been included in the national frameworks for environmental impact assessments and DRRs	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber
		M2	Key policies recognise the need for adaptation action in future growth and development as a result of the impacts of climate change	Blue	Red	Amber	Blue	Amber
		M3	National policy instruments promote adaptation at sectoral level, in line with national priorities	Blue	Amber	Amber	Amber	Blue
		M4	Adaptation is mainstreamed in insurance or alternative policy instruments to provide incentives for investment in risk prevention	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber
		M5	Climate mitigation and adaptation are being investigated in tandem	Amber	Amber	Red	Amber	Amber
		M6	Adaptation actions are sustainable (that is, meet environmental, societal and cultural needs) for their intended lifetime	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber

Key: I = Ireland, E = England, N = Northern Ireland, W = Wales, S = Scotland. Red = not acknowledged in policy, amber = acknowledged in policy but not provided for in practice, blue = acknowledged in policy and provided for in practice.

Level of agreement across the jurisdictions

The majority of criteria did not experience significant changes between rounds (Appendix 1 and 2; Table 6); however, all criteria that did experience rating changes were downgraded, with the exception of one, which was upgraded following round 2 of the survey. There were considerable levels of increased context and clarity in the justifications for all countries, both when panelists agreed and disagreed with the assessment ratings (Tables 9 and 10).

Overall, across all themes there was consensus agreement (70 per cent) from all countries in both rounds (Table 7). With the exception of Northern Ireland, there was also an increase in the level of agreement between rounds. However, Northern Ireland had the highest level of agreement with the initial assessment and it is possible that the drop-off in response rate (Table 2) played a part in the changes, with those who disagreed most strongly participating in the second round and allowing for a majority to be reached and the assessment rating changed (Table 6).

Across the five theme groupings (stakeholder engagement, policy and governance, resources, decision-making and mainstreaming) there was also a good deal of agreement with the initial assessment. The majority of

changes in ratings can be seen in the English assessment (particularly in round 1), which coincides with the increase in agreement levels by 14 per cent between rounds. However, while Ireland has a similar increase in agreement levels between rounds 1 and 2 at 11 per cent, it also has the lowest change in assessment ratings overall, suggesting that while most of the criteria assessments had a majority agreement, there was a higher degree of dissent across all criteria for Delphi participants in Ireland.

Wales has an increase of 7 per cent agreement between rounds 1 and 2 and this is reinforced in the overall total change in criteria assessments which is 7.4 per cent. Scotland has a relatively high level of total change in criteria assessments at 19.6 per cent; however this does not show in the level of increased agreement between rounds 1 and 2 which is 4 per cent. This suggests that like Ireland, there was a higher degree of dissent across the criteria for Delphi participants in Scotland. This was predominantly due to the release of a Climate Change Committee report to Scottish Parliament between rounds 1 and 2 of the Delphi survey. This report highlighted room for progress in a number of areas and likely influenced some panelist responses in round 2 of the survey.

Table 7. Criteria assessment rating changes for each country from initial assessment and between rounds 1 and 2.

Ireland				England				Northern Ireland				Wales				Scotland			
Agree		Disagree		Agree		Disagree		Agree		Disagree		Agree		Disagree		Agree		Disagree	
R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2
76%	87%	24%	13%	72%	86%	28%	14%	85%	82%	15%	18%	80%	87%	20%	13%	83%	87%	17%	13%

Table 8. Criteria assessment rating changes for each country by theme.

County	Stakeholder engagement		Policy and governance		Resources		Decision-making		Mainstreaming		Total change
	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	Both rounds
Ireland	0%	0%	0%	0%	11%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2.2%
England	50%	0%	15%	0%	22%	11%	0%	0%	17%	0%	23%
Northern Ireland	0%	0%	8%	8%	0%	0%	0%	33%	0%	17%	13.2%
Wales	0%	0%	15%	0%	0%	22%	0%	0%	0%	0%	7.4%
Scotland	0%	50%	0%	15%	0%	0%	0%	33%	0%	0%	19.6%

By country and by theme there is no trend with regards to the level of change. There were no criteria where there was not at least some rating change in one of the jurisdictions in one of the rounds.

As outlined in the methodology, Delphi panel responses were not only analysed for rating changes but also for clarity and context. The maximum score for each criterion was five, which represented a complete change in rating, while the minimum score was zero, which suggested total agreement with both the rating and full support of the justification for it. Scores in-between this indicated the level of increased clarity and added context for justifications, while in agreement with the rating. Table 8 outlines the average scores of each country in each round across the five themes.

All countries showed a decrease in the scores between rounds 1 and 2, across all themes. This suggests that the feedback of the panelists was well incorporated into the justification for each criterion and any concerns or criticisms were much better addressed following the initial analysis (Tables 9 and 10). While the analysis following round 1 confirms that the highest scores for rating changes are for those with the lowest acceptance rates among participants, it surprisingly shows no substantial correlation between the level of suggested changes to context and clarity and level of consensus for criteria justification, as would be expected. In round 2 there is a clear correlation between the score and the level of acceptance, with lower scores indicating higher acceptance rates.

Table 9. Average level of score for clarity and context as well as rating change between each round.

County	Stakeholder engagement		Policy and governance		Resources		Decision-making		Mainstreaming		Average Score	
	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2
Ireland	4	2.5	3.4	1.9	3	1.1	2	1	2.5	1	3	1.5
England	3	0.5	3	0.8	3.6	1.2	3.3	0	2.7	0.8	3.1	0.8
Northern Ireland	2.5	1	2.2	0.5	3	1	2.3	1.7	2.8	1.8	2.6	0.9
Wales	4	0.5	2.8	0.8	2.6	2.2	1.3	0	1.8	0.5	2.5	1.0
Scotland	4	2.5	3.8	1.9	4	1.3	3	2	4	0.8	3.8	1.6

Table 10. Examples of how justifications changed between rounds, following participant input.

Change in justification			
Country	Criterion code	Initial justification	Final justification
Ireland	D2	The CCAC recommendation reports are published annually and provide independent advice on the state of climate adaptation in Ireland. As Ireland has only recently begun implementing climate adaptation actions, the ability to	Consensus was reached with the majority (82%) of participants (who provided a rating) agreeing with the amber rating for this criterion. The main concerns from some of the participants were that reporting is not carried out by a fully independent entity and the reporting mechanisms in place are not robust enough (that is, lacking operational level indicators and a procedure to implement them at project or county level) to motivate change in policies and implementation across all aspects of climate adaptation. The CCAC recommendation reports are published annually and provide advice on the state of climate adaptation and resilience in Ireland; however, the CCAC is a semi-state entity and not fully independent. As Ireland has only recently begun implementing climate adaptation actions, the ability to judge their effectiveness at present is limited.

		<p>judge their effectiveness at present is limited. However, the Climate Action Delivery Board is required to monitor progress and produce quarterly reports. This criterion is rated as amber as although there are reports provided annually, there are recommendations that are the same from year to year, suggesting that the government is not addressing the issues identified by the CCAC. Also as Ireland is new to adaptation action there are aspects of adaptation (for example, mainstreaming) that have not yet been evaluated at all.</p>	<p>Although the Climate Action Delivery Board is required to monitor progress and produce quarterly reports, they met only once in 2020–2021 and have produced only a single progress report. Arrangements have been strengthened under the 2021 Climate Act, in particular, and there is now scrutiny of government performance by an Oireachtas committee on a periodic basis. The recently established and independent Office of the Planning Regulator (2019) ensures that local authorities and An Bord Pleanála support and implement government planning policy, they implement planning research, training and public awareness in order to promote the public’s engagement in the planning process and to enhance knowledge and public information about planning in Ireland. They also make recommendations on how systems and procedures could be improved or how current standards may be maintained, providing an evaluation process for local authorities, although they have no powers to enforce policies for embedded adaptation. The lack of expertise in certain aspects of planning, such as maritime functions, which they will be responsible for in the next 12–24 months, is also an issue that requires the urgent implementation of oversight structures that have requisite knowledge and expertise. This criterion is rated as amber, as although there are reports provided annually, there are recommendations that are the same from year to year, suggesting that the government is not addressing the issues identified by the CCAC. Although the first National Climate Change Strategy ran from 2000 to 2008 in Ireland there are aspects of embedded adaptation action (for example, climate proofing and climate mainstreaming) that are at an embryonic stage and have not yet been evaluated at all. These aspects of adaptation will be exceptionally difficult to measure and evaluate and will require a more robust mechanism including indicators in place for evaluation to be effective. To ensure these evaluations are useful, a requirement to implement learnings would also make this criterion more robust.</p>
<p>Scotland</p>	<p>R5</p>	<p>Scotland’s collective understanding of the risks stemming from climate change is increasing as a result of growing evidence and data from projects such as the National Flood Risk Assessment, the first, second and third UK Climate Change Risk Assessment, Dynamic Coast – Scotland’s National Coastal Change Assessment, and regional research such as the Climate Ready Clyde climate risk and opportunity assessment. This enhanced level of detail is increasingly focused on supporting the identification of adaptation options to manage risks. Within the SCCAP ongoing or planned research to support each outcome is highlighted. In addition, ClimateXChange</p>	<p>Scotland’s collective understanding of the risks stemming from climate change is increasing as a result of growing evidence and data from projects such as the National Flood Risk Assessment, the first, second and third UK Climate Change Risk Assessment, Dynamic Coast – Scotland’s National Coastal Change Assessment and the regional research such as the Climate Ready Clyde climate risk and opportunity assessment. This enhanced level of detail is increasingly focused on supporting the identification of adaptation options to manage risks. HES provides advice to Scottish Government on all matters relating to the historic environment, has the general function of investigating, caring for and promoting Scotland’s historic environment and has IRO (Independent Research Organisation) status. HES has a clear mandate to undertake research on climate change impacts and adaptation in the historic environment under SCCAP. HES has a Conservation Science Team and a Technical Research Team carrying out adaptation-relevant research. CREW (Centre of Expertise for Water) funds significant flooding research and SRP work on natural environment such as peatland, catchment management, and so on. Within the SCCAP ongoing or planned research to support each outcome is highlighted. In addition, ClimateXChange provides independent advice, research and analysis to support the Scottish Government as it develops and implements policies on adapting to the changing climate and the transition to a low carbon society. It is less apparent to what extent this research and understanding informs or underpins decision-making processes in practice. As such, initial rating of amber. In terms of support for green assessment, it was suggested that the ongoing or planned research in SCCAP outlines how understanding is to be improved in the different outcome areas. The report states that the research is to help support the implementation of adaptation policy. It was felt that SG and policymakers try very hard to ensure that the best science is underpinning decision-making and it acknowledged the work to actively commission research to fill gaps with the intention of using it to improve policy, decision making and implementation of actions. However, it was suggested that the reality is that it is the enthusiasm of individual policy officers driving through change, and there is no specific resource allocated to this work. Similarly, the SCCAP provides a good level of</p>

		<p>provides independent advice, research and analysis to support the Scottish Government as it develops and implements policies on adapting to the changing climate and the transition to a low carbon society.</p> <p>It is less apparent to what extent this research and understanding informs or underpins decision-making processes in practice. As such, initial rating of amber. Feedback requested.</p>	<p>support/sign posting to research across its outcomes. However, more support/capacity building may be needed for decision-makers to access, understand and make use of this scientific research in a way that fits their needs.</p> <p>Many respondents noted the disconnect in some areas of SG, ClimateXchange and other public bodies with regard to adaptation-related scientific research. It was also indicated ClimateXChange is very short-term/responsive and is a knowledge exchange unit to connect government to policy (research is commissioned rather than undertaken) and depends on the underpinning, strategic research undertaken at SEFARI institutions including James Hutton Institute, SRUC and RBGE through the Scottish Government’s Strategic Research Programme (SRP).</p> <p>It was felt that there is an increasing amount of information available, but potentially not the right quality to assist delivery of practical action: much is still theoretical, with less information on the most effective actions to take. In addition, the challenges between working across academic and practice were highlighted. There is a desire for more collaboration between academic institutes and local authorities for more meaningful engagement, co-production and impact (as opposed to academic researchers focusing on publications over policy development).</p> <p>Further feedback included that ScotGov needs to continue to support (and indeed enhance its support for) strategic research for climate adaptation that is important to many sectors across Scotland. CREW and CXC provide important policy-focused research funding, but longer-term, strategic funding through the SEFARI institutes (Scottish Environment, Food, Agriculture & Research Institutions) is crucial for understanding and informing decision-making on a long-term, sustainable basis. In addition, a clarification was made. There is some correction required here in terms of the description of how CXC and CREW work and are funded. They are both SG Centres of Expertise funded by RESAS with secretariats based in UoE and JHI respectively. Both draw on long-term research through RESAS’ strategic research programme (SRP) and both commission short term ‘on-demand’ policy-relevant research and post docs. It is therefore unfair to describe them differently.</p> <p>100 per cent agreed with amber rating</p>
Northern Ireland	M4	<p>Climate is not currently mainstreamed in insurance. Flood RE is available for flood insurance in Northern Ireland; however, it is only in place until 2039. Alternatives are still to be developed and additional insurance is needed for other climate risk and impact types.</p> <p>This criterion is rated amber, as although it has been acknowledged that affordable insurance is necessary, there is no widespread provision for adaptation mainstreamed in insurance.</p>	<p>Of participants who answered this criterion 60 per cent agreed with the amber rating.</p> <p>Climate is not currently mainstreamed in insurance. It should be considered as a significant barrier if there is no widespread mainstreaming in insurance. Flood RE is available for flood insurance in Northern Ireland; however, it is only in place until 2039. Alternatives are still to be developed and additional insurance is needed for other climate risk and impact types. Insurance providers are increasingly considering climate, but this risk is not often communicated. Belfast CC tried to find out about changes to insurance from climate from its broker, and while they stated that it was likely that floods in England had played a role in increased premiums, it was stated that they could not assess due to the range of other factors also being taken into consideration. Danske Bank are now including aspects of adaptation in mortgage decisions as well (largely around flooding risk).</p> <p>This criterion is still rated amber, as although it has been acknowledged that affordable insurance is necessary, there is no widespread provision for adaptation mainstreamed in insurance. However 33 per cent of people thought this should be red and 66 per cent thought it should remain amber.</p>
Wales	P2	<p>A resilient Wales is one of the seven principles of The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) Act (2015) and in order to provide for</p>	<p>Consensus was reached with all (100%) participants (who provided a rating) agreeing with the green rating for this criterion.</p> <p>A resilient Wales is one of the seven principles of The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) Act (2015) and in order to provide for a resilient Wales, a Welsh climate change adaptation plan (<i>Prosperity for All: A climate conscious Wales</i>) was published in 2019.</p> <p>This criterion is rated green as there is a national climate adaptation policy</p>

		<p>a resilient Wales, a Welsh climate change adaptation plan (<i>Prosperity for All: A climate conscious Wales</i>) was published in 2019.</p> <p>This criterion is rated green as there is a national climate adaptation policy for Wales.</p>	<p>for Wales; however, the effectiveness of this policy may not be adequate as it is not integral to all development activity and decision-making in Wales.</p>
England	P3	<p>The Department of Environment Energy and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) is responsible for overarching UK policy, while the Environment Agency (EA) shares the responsibility for climate adaptation in England, although who is responsible for specific roles and responsibilities is unclear.</p> <p>This criterion is assessed as green, as England has central administration bodies responsible for adaptation policymaking</p>	<p>Consensus was reached, with all (100%) participants (who provided a rating) in agreement with the amber rating for this criterion.</p> <p>The Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) is responsible for overarching UK policymaking. However, while DEFRA is officially the central coordinating point for adaptation policy across government, it lacks the levers needed to influence adaptation policymaking in many sector areas, resulting in some questions over ownership of adaptation policy across government. Examples of this are embedded aspects of adaptation planning in strategic departments such as health when considering heatwave plans or the Environment Agency (EA) when it comes to flood risk management, erosion and drought. embedded practice occurs in some areas, a systematic approach to climate change adaptation is not evident.</p> <p>However, although DEFRA plays this role, they currently do not have the resources to do it in a way that is fit for purpose. At the time of the first CCRA the Adapting to Climate Change Team in Defra was 40 strong; this has now been reduced to a handful of people, who also have to work across other government departments on adaptation.</p> <p>This criterion is assessed as amber, as although England has a central administration body, which is in theory, responsible for adaptation policymaking, they do not have control over adaption policymaking in all areas and the resources being provided to it are not adequately funded or empowered enough to probe/ liaise across government departments.</p>

Discussion

Public policies often fail to realise their stated intentions, with policy goals often staying on paper because of the barriers that exist in implementing them.⁴² The analysis of the national adaptation policy assessments showed that there are common barriers across all of the UK and Ireland, the most significant of which is the lack of resources provided to achieve national policy ambitions.

Stakeholder engagement

Representative stakeholder engagement is essential in addressing the disconnect between different stakeholders (scientists, policymakers, businesses, community groups and so on), acquiring local buy-in, and in producing good quality adaptation planning.⁴³ Without these different perspectives policies can promote a limited view of climate impacts and opportunities, and risk perpetuating

inequality. While there is evidence of mechanisms in place to promote stakeholder engagement across all jurisdictions, including national conversations, citizens’ assemblies and public consultations, such as seen in Wales and Ireland, these often only include elements of climate adaptation, and none currently enables the level of engagement required. As noted by some participants (Table 11), the way in which stakeholders are selected for this engagement can also impact how representative and valuable their input into the final outcomes are.

Policy and governance

Within policy and governance, a clear-cut national agenda and strong leadership provides the structure, guidance and impetus to enable action at all levels. However, approaches that are too centralised can hamper local initiatives and create dependencies, highlighting the need for top-down and bottom-up approaches in tandem.⁴⁴ Multi-level governance and the coordination between

42 PL Hupe ‘The thesis of incongruent implementation: revisiting Pressman and Wildavsky’ (2011) 26(1) *Public Policy and Administration* 63.

43 J Sun and K Yang ‘The wicked problem of climate change: a new approach based on social mess and fragmentation’ (2016) 8(12) *Sustainability* 1312.

44 H Bulkeley *et al.* ‘Governing climate change transnationally: assessing the evidence from a database of sixty initiatives’ (2012) 30(4) *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy* 591.

Table 11. Delphi panel participant comments on stakeholder engagement.

Country	Participant	Comment
Ireland	8	'Defining who are relevant stakeholders is very important ... the ambiguity reflects this problem at a national level where adaptation policy and implementation is concerned. Generally, only high-level representatives (such as government) are considered stakeholders, except when the National Dialogue on Climate Action is mentioned, which was a much broader subset of society. As a subset, though, it is certainly not ample: engagement is not in any way a "representative" sample upon which to base policy.'
Northern Ireland	2	'Adequate stakeholder engagement and representation is critical for sustainable adaptation planning and I have not seen evidence that the appropriate resource has been given to acquiring the necessary level of engagement in Northern Ireland. I have questions about how stakeholders, involved in NICCAP1 and NICCAP2, were chosen and therefore would be concerned about the risk posed by unintentionally excluding key stakeholders from the entirety of the process as a result.'
Wales	7	'There was only high-level stakeholders' engagement for the development of the National Adaptation Plan which in itself is too high level. All potential measures and actions fall on stakeholders to take forward. These were not agreed, for example resources were not allocated to support the delivery of these actions.'

organisations and actors at different levels is important for bringing deliberation to climate adaptation planning,⁴⁵ whether in the case of public, private or third sectors.⁴⁶ In this study all jurisdictions have shown ambition to progress climate adaptation, with national strategies and policies underpinned by legislation (in the case of Northern Ireland this has been put in place since the Delphi panel ended), and a monitoring and evaluation framework in place. Despite this, governance structures often promote siloed working, with resource restrictions inhibiting meaningful cross-sector and multi-level collaboration, which in turn has a direct impact on justice and equity issues which are not being adequately addressed (Table 12).

A lack of shared responsibility for climate adaptation means that perceptions are often filtered through existing power structures, so that outcomes are compatible with

their economic and political goals.⁴⁷ This can cause inefficient adaptation actions and even maladaptation, widening the climate justice gap in some areas. This is highlighted in Northern Ireland, where the lack of climate legislation in place showed a knock-on effect on subsequent policy documents, with climate justice and equity issues unacknowledged. However, following the implementation of the Climate Change Act (Northern Ireland) 2022, a Just Transition Commission has been provided for. Climate adaptation policies have an opportunity to investigate inequalities in society and to adopt measures which reduce the impacts of climate change to those who are most at risk. When policies allow for social disadvantage to be considered as a factor alongside economic and environmental factors when implementing adaptation plans and providing resources, climate adaptation can help reduce inequalities in society.

Table 12. Delphi panel participant comments on policy and governance: climate justice and equity.

Country	Participant	Comment
Ireland	16	'I think the whole Just Transition conversation is viewed as a wealthy or middle-class aspiration rather than anything actually meaningful for the more vulnerable in society or how we include them.'
Northern Ireland	7	'Notwithstanding the move towards a just transition, it is accepted that there are currently no processes in place to consider climate change actions and specific impacts on vulnerable groups.'
England	6	'I just don't think climate justice/social vulnerability is really taken seriously. There are some instances where it feeds into policy and decision-making, but this is not across the board.'
Scotland	10	'Often intervention is focused on the most vulnerable area of an asset rather than in conjunction with what the wider impact might be with the most vulnerable groups.'
Wales	1	'... but the reality is that not all PSBs have climate adaptation as a priority and few have evaluated vulnerability with regards climate action. Pan Wales research on community vulnerability remains unpublished owing to sensitivities.'

45 Corfee-Morlot *et al.* (Note 9 above); T Measham *et al.* 'Adapting to climate change through local municipal planning: barriers and challenges' (2011) 16(8) *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change* 889.

46 E Tompkins and H Eakin 'Managing private and public adaptation to climate change' (2012) 22(1) *Global Environmental Change* 3.

47 LO Næss *et al.* 'Institutional adaptation to climate change: flood responses at the municipal level in Norway' (2005) 15(2) *Global Environmental Change* 125.

Table 13. Delphi panel participant comments on resources: staff and financing.

Ireland	12	'Successive governments have struggled to understand and meet the financial cost of implementing climate adaptation measures.'
Northern Ireland	2	'Appropriate financing specifically for climate adaptation across sectors does appear to be lacking. Beyond DAERA there is no strong focus on delivery of climate change adaptation initiatives which has led to, on a number of occasions, my organisation having to proposition government departments to take necessary steps to fund valuable and critical climate adaptation projects linked directly to policy goals or seek financial help from other funders beyond NI government bodies and their related agencies.'
England	7	'The level of funding in England is woefully inadequate as highlighted by the CCRA3.'
Scotland	2	'Big funding and skills gap. Continuous under resourcing tied to increased deliverable is putting stress on the professionals and means that collaboration can be difficult and not transparent. Also means there is still a focus on mitigation.'
Wales	3	'The funding deficit is one of the biggest challenges facing the sector and the impact cannot be underestimated. For climate adaptation to be realised, there is a very real need for much more staff and financial resource.'

A lack of resource for implementation has also hindered the emergence of leaders in climate adaptation across all jurisdictions. This has impacted particularly strongly on local scales, where diverse stakeholder involvement and strong leadership are often needed to drive action.⁴⁸ Without financial and personnel support, leaders cannot step forward to initiate and manage climate adaptation and no long-term gains will be made.⁴⁹ However, all five jurisdictions have provided for some degree of wider transboundary cooperation to address climate impacts. This tends to be primarily focused on cooperation within and between the UK and Ireland, and is likely driven by the current and historic political and cultural connections across the area, shared infrastructure such as transport and energy networks that run across national boundaries and similarity of shared climate risks and impacts.

Resources

With the exception of some policies (Ireland, England and Scotland) that support advances in obtaining new evidence and communicating it to wider audiences, across the theme of resources all jurisdictions are in almost total agreement in their assessments, which highlight a substantial lack of provision for staff and financing, capacity building, information and data gathering and communication and guidance.

Principal among these is the need for appropriate resourcing, which has not been acknowledged in policy in any jurisdiction, and is the only factor that has unanimous agreement between all panelists in all rounds of the survey, highlighting how strongly this is felt by stakeholders

working in all aspects of climate adaptation (Table 13). Doing nothing is the most expensive and worst option. However, without clear government understanding and plans which acknowledge the scale of the financial cost of implementing adaptation measures, policy goals will never be reached, and the adaptation gap will continue to grow. This lack of funding is often exacerbated by an 'adaptive capacity' gap between the perception that people are able and need to adapt and actually taking adaptive action to the level predicted to be needed, leading to an 'adaptation deficit'.⁵⁰ By promoting and funding the education, empowerment and engagement of all stakeholders across every level and putting in place mechanisms to train practitioners, policy across Britain and Ireland can provide for capacity building, something it is currently failing to do.

A thorough scientific evidence and knowledge base and the ability to communicate the evidence is a prerequisite for effective adaptation action. While there is evidence of new scientific research in all jurisdictions, including initiatives such as Climate Ireland and the UK Climate Change Risk Assessment, which is mandated by law, much of the research carried out is done on a project basis and does not incorporate local knowledge. There are still many gaps in the evidence available, and the lack of long-term strategic funding to provide a robust knowledge base is a failing in all jurisdictions. Access to evidence-based information and local knowledge can be used to discern gaps and inform decision-making and is a central aspect of climate successful adaptation.⁵¹

Across all jurisdictions there is a need for more effective communication and engagement strategies and learning and support networks. The way evidence is presented can influence decision-making and therefore adaptation

48 J Gupta and E Bergsma 'The adaptive capacity wheel: a method to assess the inherent characteristics of institutions to enable the adaptive capacity of society' (2010) 13(6) *Environmental Science & Policy* 459.

49 A Becker and E Kretsch 'The leadership void for climate adaptation planning: case study of the Port of Providence (Rhode Island, United States)' (2019) 7(29) *Frontiers in Earth Science* <doi: 10.3389/feart.2019.00029> (last accessed 11 March 2023).

50 Berrang-Ford *et al.* (Note 6 above); Lesnikowski *et al.* (Note 31 above); Gawith and Daigneault (Note 31 above).

51 K Lonsdale *et al.* *Attributes of Well-Adapting Organisations* (London, UK Climate Impacts Programme 2010).

Table 14. Delphi panel participant comments on decision-making.

Country	Participant	Comment
Northern Ireland	4	'I think to date, we're still waiting to see any meaningful usage or connection between the risks in the CCRA and the actions in the NICCAP.'
Northern Ireland	9	'This is chiefly reflective of the current political uncertainty and budget uncertainty – we have no assurances yet of implementation of the incoming Climate Change Act, resourcing of the Green Growth strategy etc.'
Scotland	5	'The justification narrative is clear that the selection process for priority adaptation options was not transparent and lacking an appraisal process or M&E framework and so the rating can only be assessed as red.'
Scotland	6	'...justification should have provided any evidence of prioritised CCA options. Adaptation struggles due to the absence of objectives so that adaptation options can be developed.'

solutions.⁵² Therefore, climate science communication that is tailored to the audience is vital in order to ensure the relevance of evidence to the decision context.⁵³

Decision-making

Good decision-making underpins successful adaptation at all levels. The assessments highlighted that in all jurisdictions, support to ensure that decision-makers have the resources, capacity and guidance to select, assess and prioritise adaptation options in an equitable manner is not provided for in national-level policies. In Scotland and Northern Ireland the need to ensure that priority adaptation options are selected based on robust, equitable and transparent methods is not even acknowledged in national policy (Table 14). Decision-making without these crucial elements increases the likelihood of inequity and maladaptation across all levels as national policy often sets the standard for sub-national efforts.

When faced with uncertainty many decision-makers at both national and local levels have employed approaches whereby actions are delayed in order to gather more information, or enhance adaptive capacity.⁵⁴ However, as seen through the increasingly severe and frequent climate impacts across the UK and Ireland, the 'wait and see' approach is not always feasible, and will cost more in resources and time than beginning action now. To combat deep uncertainty, decision-makers can begin by focusing on 'low-regret' measures (that is, actions that are relatively low cost and provide relatively large benefits

under a range of predicted future climate scenarios) that build some degree of resilience.⁵⁵

Mainstreaming

Mainstreaming is essential to avoid maladaptive policies that lead to detriment in other sectors or areas. Policies across all of the jurisdictions generally acknowledge the need for adaptation to be mainstreamed into 'business-as-usual' and linkages considered across multiple sectors and levels. However, the assessments highlight that there is still a significant adaptation gap in all regions (Table 15), with England and Northern Ireland failing to acknowledge the need for adaptation to be recognised in key policies and investigated in tandem with mitigation, respectively, in policy. How adaptation is perceived by society and the lack of provision for sustainable adaptation initiatives considered in key frameworks and insurance instruments, across the UK and Ireland are a major barrier to successful adaptation.

Although there have been efforts made (Scotland and Ireland) to align sectoral adaptation with national priorities, this does not constitute the depth or breadth of work needed to mainstream adaptation into stakeholders' everyday decision-making. Mainstreaming at this level requires national reinforcement to manage the process and ensure coordination, avoiding conflict both vertically and horizontally within the governance structure, while also providing the resources to allow for effective adaptation.⁵⁶

What we can learn from our neighbours

There are a lot of similarities between the different themes even after the changes between rounds of the Delphi survey. However, there are also key differences across the jurisdictions, with some themes much better

52 Daron *et al.* (Note 32 above).

53 S Tang and S Dessai 'Usable science? The UK climate projections 2009 and decision support for adaptation planning' (2012) 4(4) *Weather Climate, and Society* <doi:10.1175/wcas-1.1> (last accessed 11 November 2022); L Jones *et al.* 'Ensuring climate information guides long-term development' (2015) 5 *Nature Climate Change* 812.

54 JA Curry and PJ Webster 'Climate science and the uncertainty monster' (2011) 92(12) *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 1667; S Hallegatte 'Strategies to adapt to an uncertain climate change' (2009) 19(2) *Global Environmental Change* 240; RL Wilby and G Darch 'Uncertainty in hydrologic and water resources modelling' in LO Mearns *et al.* (eds) *Uncertainty in Climate Change Research: An Integrated Approach* (Springer, Switzerland 2021).

55 RL Wilby. 'Well informed adaptation decision making under uncertainty' (2022) Working paper No 12 <<https://www.climatecouncil.ie/media/climatechangeadvisorycouncil/contentassets/publications/Working%20Paper%20No.%2012%20Decision%20making%20under%20uncertainty.pdf>> (last accessed 30 January 2023).

56 A Hunt and P Watkiss 'Climate change impacts and adaptation in cities: a review of the literature' (2011) 104 *Climatic Change* 13.

Table 15. Delphi panel participant comments on mainstreaming.

Country	Participant	Comment
Ireland	13	'The trade-offs and conflicts are not appreciated and piecemeal policies are likely to throw up unintended consequences. A fully integrated approach involving the impacts-mitigation-adaptation nexus is badly needed.'
Northern Ireland	16	'... really there are no sectoral plans to speak of at all as it stands, and the NICCAP requires only government departments to state actions. The proposed DAERA legislation currently makes no provision for them either, despite anecdotal indications that some may be being considered. Further to that, there is little to no practical support for sectors, beyond some initial funding through CNI, NIEL, BITC and KNIB.'
England	1	'... mitigation is firmly centre stage and adaptation significantly behind. I feel less positive about how much this is shifting, so have put red.'
Scotland	6	'I agree that national policy instruments lay statutory duties across public bodies and increase the awareness of adaptation across sectors. However, I don't see adaptation as in line with national priorities.'
Wales	4	'... but examples are initiatives that have little national impact. Adaptation isn't being taken seriously and it would be wrong to suggest otherwise.'

addressed within policy and policy instruments in particular jurisdictions. The reason for many of the differences in policy in the four jurisdictions of the UK is because climate adaptation is a devolved matter, with each respective government responsible for their own adaptation planning and implementation. While Scotland, England and Wales have generally similar ratings across the criteria, Northern Ireland has a good deal more criteria not acknowledged in policy. These differences are seen between Northern Ireland and Ireland as well, even though this is a shared geographical island with almost identical environmental risks and vulnerabilities and very similar cultural traditions and social practices.

Without national legislation or independent monitoring in place, Northern Ireland has seen a knock-on effect of fewer essential criteria for good climate adaptation acknowledged in policy. This is exacerbated by the current political situation that has seen the absence of a working executive in Northern Ireland for a major part of the past five years. This highlights the need for a stable government and shows how legislation can be a vehicle for progress in adaptation. Recent changes to the climate adaptation legislation in Northern Ireland since the Delphi survey ended and following the analysis by the authors have meant that two of the criteria under national policy (P3 and P4) are now rated blue and one criterion (P11) is now rated amber, something which the authors believe will have a positive knock-on effect on other criteria and on adaptation action within this jurisdiction in general.

The length of time national legislation has been in place also appears to be a contributing factor within the assessments. Both Ireland and Wales have a larger number of criteria rated blue than England and Scotland. This directly corresponds to the fact that legislation on climate change has only been introduced in Ireland and Wales since 2015, while in England and Scotland climate change legislation has been in place since 2008 and 2009

respectively. This suggests that following the introduction of legislation there is a period of increased top-down support; however, this momentum does not appear to remain sustained over time.

As evidenced across the assessments in Ireland and the UK, acknowledgement of the necessity of adaptation in policy does not always translate into action on the ground. There needs to be an investment of resources and time from public, private and third sectors, so that the ambitions of policy are recognised in practice, and climate adaptation does not become just lip service.

Reflections and limitations of the Delphi panel process

The Delphi panel process employed during this study highlighted the potential of the Delphi panel as a communication technique. Panellists gave clear feedback on the fact that they found this to be an extremely useful learning experience with some stating that they 'appreciated the range of perspectives that were outlined within the criteria justifications', as well as an opportunity to input their own knowledge of climate adaptation policy in their respective jurisdictions.

Involving not only researchers/academics and practitioners, as many other assessments do,⁵⁷ but also including those working in the private and third sectors has allowed for a deeper and more robust investigation of adaptation policy and how it impacts on a range of actors.

57 CCC (2023) *Annual Progress Report: Progress in Adapting to Climate Change*. Available at: Progress in adapting to climate change - 2023 Report to Parliament - Climate Change Committee < <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/2023-progress-report-to-parliament/> > (last accessed 20 June 2023); CCAC (2022) *Climate Change Advisory Council Annual Review*. Available at: <https://www.climatecouncil.ie/media/climatechangeadvisorycouncil/contentassets/documents/Final%20Copy%20edited%20version%20for%20website%20publication.pdf> (last accessed 10 January 2023).

Delphi panel participants provided valuable insights on their own experiences of how adaptation policy is failing or succeeding to enable climate action in each jurisdiction. The level of disagreement across some of the criteria suggests that there are clear differences in the experiences of different actors within the same jurisdiction and a level of dissent on how policy can better address the current challenges that climate adaptation is facing.

A vast majority of participants felt that policy was a crucial driving factor in the progression of adaptation, but there was also a feeling that it does not go far enough and, as highlighted by Flood et al.⁵⁸ in their recent study, there is also a need for bottom-up deliberative engagement that allows for a wide range of representative input, acknowledges the power dynamics currently involved in decision-making around climate adaptation and inspires a more transformative approach.

Although this experience has been hugely beneficial for both knowledge gathering and knowledge exchange, there are also limitations to this method. This was an extremely detailed survey by Delphi panel standards and involved a substantial time commitment from participants. This led to a drop-off rate in three of the five jurisdictions in the second Delphi round, particularly in Northern Ireland (Table 2). This in turn meant that consensus was reached much more easily due to the lower number of participants. The limited and relatively recent work in climate adaptation in the UK and Ireland has also meant that the number of respondents who were knowledgeable in adaptation policy and also available to participate in the survey was limited in some jurisdictions and subsequently meant that some participants had less than four years' experience of working in climate adaptation. These participants were less likely than other, more experienced, panellists to contribute comprehensive justifications when completing the survey.

Further work is needed to describe and unpack the full range of results from specific criteria assessments, in particular the detail on what governance processes and policies are currently enabling adaptation in each country and how this can be replicated in other areas.

Conclusions and recommendations

This article has presented a novel approach to evaluating national climate adaptation policies, using the assessment framework of good practice, developed as part of the

research, and the application of a modified Delphi panel method using both quantitative and qualitative results.

The framework involved a comprehensive review of the literature as to what constitutes best practice with regards to climate adaptation and was distilled down to 33 essential criteria that are vital for successful adaptation that promotes equity and justice.

While the use of the Delphi method can raise issues with regards to the influence of response rates on the level of consensus and discord, this was not found to be a significant factor in our study, even in jurisdictions (Northern Ireland) where there was a higher panelist drop-off rate. The Delphi method is particularly suited to addressing complex issues and while the iterative method can be time-consuming to administer, the level of detail acquired through the use of the modified format of the Delphi survey in this study was substantial, allowing for detailed policy assessments in each jurisdiction. Feedback from participants in the survey also indicated that they found it to be a very useful learning experience that widened their perspectives on national climate adaptation policy. Overall, the research highlighted broad similarities in the assessments of the different jurisdictions, and while some differ around individual criteria there is a general trend that while policy in general acknowledges the importance of different adaptation aspects, it does not provide for this in practice, with a noticeable absence of resources and decision-making ability across all jurisdictions. The assessments also outline the importance of 'top-down' drivers to ensure key elements of adaptation at all levels. This research sought to provide countries with a baseline for their current status across essential adaptation criteria and support governments in enabling climate adaptation within their respective jurisdictions.

Further assessments in Northern Ireland represent an excellent opportunity to do a longitudinal evaluation on how much underpinning legislation can enable climate adaptation in practice. It is clear that while 'bottom-up' adaptation and the full involvement of stakeholders and the public is now recognised as essential for effective implementation,⁵⁹ 'top-down' drivers are equally important for successful climate adaptation.

58 S Flood et al. 'Imagining climate resilient futures: a layered Delphi panel approach' (2023) 147 *Futures* 103100. < <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2023.103100> > (last accessed 12 June 2023).

59 H Pallett, J Chilvers and T Hargreaves 'Mapping participation: a systematic analysis of diverse public participation in the UK energy system' (2019) 2 *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space* 590; U Felt and M Fochler 'Slim futures and the fat pill: civic imaginations of innovation and governance in an engagement setting' (2011) 20 *Science as Culture* 307.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Initial assessment results before the Delphi survey

Factor	Sub-factor	Code	Criteria	I	E	N	W	S
Stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder engagement	S1	Representative stakeholder involvement throughout the entire climate adaptation process, from the creation of adaptation policy to the implementation and evaluation of adaptation plans	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
		S2	A dedicated process in place to facilitate inclusive stakeholder involvement in the preparation of adaptation policies	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Blue
Policy and governance	National policy	P1	A central administration body officially in charge of adaptation policy making	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
		P2	A national climate adaptation policy	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
		P3	Country level legislation in place to underpin adaptation policy (including frameworks and strategies and so on)	Blue	Blue	Red	Blue	Blue
		P4	Independent monitoring and evaluation of national policy	Blue	Blue	Red	Blue	Blue
	Leadership & co-ordination of roles and responsibilities	P5	Horizontal (cross-sectoral) coordination mechanisms exist within the governance system, with division of responsibilities and SMART objectives and the alignment of policies	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Blue	Blue
		P6	Vertical (multi-level) coordination mechanisms exist in the governance system, enabling all levels of administration from local to national to influence policy-making	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
		P7	Creation of spaces for leaders of climate adaptation to emerge across scales	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
		P8	Climate adaptation is scalable, able to be tailored to different levels	Yellow	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Yellow
		P9	Transparent climate finance with regards to adaptation initiatives	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red
		P10	Transboundary cooperation (either existing or planned) to work together to address common challenges with other countries	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	Climate justice and equity	P11	Domestic justice and equity issues (economic, social, environmental and cultural), relevant to each country, are recognised in national-level climate change policy and implementation (for example through decision-making)	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
		P12	Processes are in place to allow actions to reduce any identified differences and/or ensure the benefits of interventions accrue to the most vulnerable	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
		P13	Climate adaptation policy development, implementation and review is fully transparent	Blue	Blue	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Resource	Staff and financing	R1	Appropriate financing (enough to cover the cost of policy actions) is being applied to climate adaptation to achieve policy goals at all levels of governance	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
		R2	Accessible long-term and self-sustaining resources are available to support policy goals at increasing climate resilience (that is, funding, infrastructure, human resources)	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
	Capacity building and understanding the capability of decision-makers and action-takers	R3	Policy supports education, empowerment and engagement of stakeholders at all levels of decision making and action taking in relation to adaptation	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
		R4	Mechanisms exist to recruit and train practitioners with the specific skills required to undertake complex climate adaptation	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
	Information and data	R5	The policy supports advances in scientific research to improve understanding and inform decision-making	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Yellow
		R6	Guidance on how to employ climate adaptation information is provided at sub-national levels	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
	Communication and guidance	R7	Communication and engagement strategies included within the policy that utilise multiple platforms in order to reach diverse stakeholders	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Blue	Yellow
		R8	Recognition in the policy that climate change is an international issue and that adaptation strategies must look beyond national boundaries (that is, the policy ensures the international aspect of adaptation is considered at decision-making levels)	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Blue
		R9	Learning and support networks are available to enable all decision-makers in producing and implementing appropriate climate adaptation policies	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow

Decision-making	Decision-making	D1	Priority adaptation options are identified, prioritised and selected based on robust, equitable and transparent methods (for example using decision support tools)						
		D2	An evaluation process is in place to assess the effectiveness of actions taken across all aspects of climate adaptation (that is, from stakeholder engagement to mainstreaming)						
		D3	The policy recognises that adaptation is an iterative and flexible process that accounts for new information and experience						
Mainstreaming	Mainstreaming	M1	Consideration of climate change adaptation included in the national frameworks for environmental impact assessments and DRRs						
		M2	Key policies recognise the need for adaptation action in future growth and development as a result of the impacts of climate change						
		M3	National policy instruments promote adaptation at sectoral level, in line with national priorities						
		M4	Adaptation is mainstreamed in insurance or alternative policy instruments to provide incentives for investments in risk prevention						
		M5	Climate mitigation and adaptation are being investigated in tandem						
		M6	Adaptation actions are sustainable (that is, meet environmental, societal and cultural needs) for their intended lifetime						

Key: I = Ireland, E = England, N = Northern Ireland, W = Wales, S = Scotland. Red = not acknowledged in policy, amber = acknowledged in policy but not provided for in practice, blue = acknowledged in policy and provided for in practice.

Appendix 2. Round 1 assessment results after the Delphi survey.

Factor	Sub-factor	Code	Criteria	I	E	N	W	S
Stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder engagement	S1	Representative stakeholder involvement throughout the entire climate adaptation process, from the creation of adaptation policy to the implementation and evaluation of adaptation plans					
		S2	A dedicated process in place to facilitate inclusive stakeholder involvement in the preparation of adaptation policies					
Policy and governance	National policy	P1	A central administration body officially in charge of adaptation policy making					
		P2	A national climate adaptation policy					
		P3	Country level legislation in place to underpin adaptation policy (including frameworks and strategies)					
		P4	Independent monitoring and evaluation of national policy					
	Leadership and co-ordination of roles and responsibilities	P5	Horizontal (cross-sectoral) coordination mechanisms exist within the governance system, with division of responsibilities and SMART objectives and the alignment of policies					
		P6	Vertical (multi-level) coordination mechanisms exist in the governance system, enabling all levels of administration from local to national to influence policymaking					
		P7	Creation of spaces for leaders of climate adaptation to emerge across scales					
		P8	Climate adaptation is scalable, able to be tailored to different levels					
		P9	Transparent climate finance with regards to adaptation initiatives					
		P10	Transboundary cooperation (either existing or planned) to work together to address common challenges with other countries					
	Climate justice and equity	P11	Domestic justice and equity issues (economic, social, environmental and cultural), relevant to each country, are recognised in national-level climate change policy and implementation (for example through decision-making)					
		P12	Processes are in place to allow actions to reduce any identified differences and/or ensure the benefits of interventions accrue to the most vulnerable					
		P13	Climate adaptation policy development, implementation and review is fully transparent					
Staff and financing	R1	Appropriate financing (enough to cover the cost of policy actions) is being applied to climate adaptation to achieve policy goals at all levels of governance						
	R2	Accessible long-term and self-sustaining resources are available to support policy goals at increasing climate resilience (that is, funding, infrastructure, human resources)						

Resources	Capacity building and understanding the capability of decision-makers and action-takers	R3	Policy supports education, empowerment and engagement of stakeholders at all levels of decision-making and action-taking in relation to adaptation	Blue	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	
		R4	Mechanisms exist to recruit and train practitioners with the specific skills required to undertake complex climate adaptation	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	
	Information and data	R5	The policy supports advances in scientific research to improve understanding and inform decision-making	Blue	Blue	Amber	Blue	Amber	
		R6	Guidance for how to employ climate adaptation information is provided at sub-national levels	Blue	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	
	Communication and guidance	R7	Communication and engagement strategies included within the policy that utilise multiple platforms in order to reach diverse stakeholders	Amber	Amber	Amber	Blue	Amber	
		R8	Recognition within the policy that climate change is an international issue and that adaptation strategies must look beyond national boundaries (that is, the policy ensures the international aspect of adaptation is considered at decision-making levels)	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Blue	
		R9	Learning and support networks are available to enable all decision-makers in producing and implementing appropriate climate adaptation policies	Blue	Blue	Amber	Amber	Amber	
	Decision-making	Decision-making	D1	Priority adaptation options are identified, prioritised and selected based on robust, equitable and transparent methods (for example using decision support tools)	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber
			D2	An evaluation process is in place to assess the effectiveness of actions taken across all aspects of climate adaptation (that is, from stakeholder engagement to mainstreaming)	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber
D3			The policy recognises that adaptation is an iterative and flexible process that accounts for new information and experience	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	
Mainstreaming	Mainstreaming	M1	Consideration of climate change adaptation been included in the national frameworks for environmental impact assessments and DRRs	Amber	Amber	Red	Amber	Amber	
		M2	Key policies recognise the need for adaptation action in future growth and development as a result of the impacts of climate change	Blue	Red	Amber	Blue	Amber	
		M3	National policy instruments promote adaptation at sectoral level, in line with national priorities	Blue	Amber	Amber	Amber	Blue	
		M4	Adaptation is mainstreamed in insurance or alternative policy instruments to provide incentives for investment in risk prevention	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	
		M5	Climate mitigation and adaptation are being investigated in tandem	Amber	Amber	Red	Amber	Amber	
		M6	Adaptation actions are sustainable (that is, meet environmental, societal and cultural needs) for their intended lifetime	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	Amber	

Key: I = Ireland, E = England, N = Northern Ireland, W = Wales, S = Scotland. Red = not acknowledged in policy, amber = acknowledged in policy but not provided for in practice, blue = acknowledged in policy and provided for in practice.